

PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS AS TOOL FOR DATA REDUCTION WITH AN APPLICATION

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Abstract

The recent trends in collecting huge datasets have posed a great challenge that is brought by the high dimensionality and aggravated by the presence of irrelevant dimensions. Machine learning models for regression is recognized as a convenient way of improving the estimation for empirical models. Popular machine learning models is support vector regression (SVR). However, the usage of principal component analysis (PCA) as a variable reduction method along with SVR is suggested. The principal component analysis helps in building a predictive model that is simple as it contains the smallest number of variables and efficient. In this paper, we investigate the competence of SVR with PCA to explore its performance for a more accurate estimation. Simulation study and Renal Failure (RF) data of SVR optimized by four different kernel functions; linear, polynomial, radial basis, and sigmoid functions using *R* software, version (Rx64 3.2.5) to compare the behavior of ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR models for different sample sizes ranges from small, moderate to large such as: 50, 100, and 150. The performance criteria are root mean squared error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination R^2 showed the superiority of ϵ -SVR over ν -SVR. Furthermore, the implementation of SVR after employing PCA improves the results. Also, the simulation results showed that the best performing kernel function is the linear kernel. For real data the results showed that the best kernels are linear and radial basis function. It is also clear that, with ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR, the RMSE values for almost kernel functions decreased with increasing sample size. Therefore, the performance of ϵ -SVR improved after applying PCA. In addition sample size $n = 50$ gave good results for linear and radial kernel.

Keywords: Kernel Functions, Principal Component Analysis, Renal failure, Support Vector Regression.

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1. Introduction

The recent trends in collecting huge and diverse data sets, such as documents; videos and digital images; financial time series and gene expressions and DNA copy numbers, have posed a great challenge that is brought by the curse of dimensionality and aggravated by the presence of irrelevant dimensions in many tasks such as predictive modeling [1]. An attractive solution is to use the principal component analysis (PCA), one of the oldest and the most popular and well known methods for reducing the dimensionality of many raw data sets having a high-dimension space in an interpretable way such that the information (variability) in the data is preserved as much as possible [2].

In contrast to traditional scientific approaches where simple predictive models are built to fit the given data set, PCA procedure helps in building a predictive model that is simple as it contains the smallest number of predictive variables and efficient that accounts for as much of the information «explained variation» as possible [3, 4]. PCA converts a set of correlated variables into uncorrelated ones using an orthogonal transformation [5]. Due to presence of some correlations among input variables and the appropriate preprocessing transformations of high dimensional input data can

increase the overall performance of algorithms, the dimensionality reduction or so called the feature extraction allows one to restrict the entire input space to a sub-space of lower dimensionality [6]. Owing to its superior properties over other linear dimension reduction (LDR) methods [4], PCA find successful applications in many fields including image segmentation [7], genome-wide expression studies [4], and deep learning [8].

One of the most robust prediction methods in machine learning is Support Vector Machines (SVMs) which is derived from statistical learning theory [9]. SVMs are supervised learning models with associated learning algorithms for solving both supervised classification and regression problems or more colloquially learning from examples [10]. SVR and its variations have been continually developed to strengthen their effectiveness in different applications [11]. PCA is widely used as a dimensionality reduction or a feature selection method in the framework of SVM [12].

Support vector regression (ε -SVR) is the extension of SVM classification to handle regression (functional approximation) problems by measuring the error of approximation instead of the margin used in classification [13]. Unlike traditional regression methods, SVR learns a model to describe a variable's importance for characterizing the input-output relationship (dependency, mapping or function) instead of making assumptions on the linear data distribution of input data that might not be accurate. For additional advantages see [10].

The successful application of PCA to SVR in various problems has encouraged its adaptation, which is mainly due to [14] who showed that kernel PCA-SVR is better in reconstructing a more accurate transmembrane potentials distribution on the ventricular surface than PCA-SVR for reconstruction of cardiac transmembrane potentials [15]. Showed that the integration of Vector Quantization with Principle Component Analysis techniques VQ/PCA with SVR model increases the prediction accuracy of SVR for sulfur content prediction in hydrodesulphurization process [16]. Showed that PCA-SVR using radial basis function (RBF) produced less mean average precision MAP (%), mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE) and RMSE than single SVR in the financial time series forecasting model.

In this paper, two procedures were conducted within the practical aspect. The first procedure employs PCA with ε -SVR. The other also employs PCA but with v -SVR.

2. Materials and methods

PCA finds smaller number of uncorrelated components from high dimensional original inputs by calculating the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix. Given a set of m dimensional input vectors $x_i = (x_i(1), x_i(2), \dots, x_i(m))^T$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. PCA is a transformation of x_i into a new vector y_i given below

$$y_i = U^T x_i. \quad (1)$$

Where U is the $m \times m$ orthogonal matrix whose j -th column u_j is the j -th eigenvector of the sample covariance matrix $C = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i x_i^T$. In other words, PCA solves the following eigenvalue/eigenvector problem:

$$\lambda_j u_j = C u_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (2)$$

where λ_j is one of the eigenvalues of C and u_j is the corresponding eigenvector.

Based on the estimated u_j , the components of y_i are calculated as an orthogonal transformation of x_i as follows:

$$y_i = (j) = u_j^T x_i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (3)$$

The new components are called principal components. By using only the first several eigenvectors sorted in a descending order of eigenvalues, the number of principal components in y_i can be reduced [17].

Support Vector Regression (SVR) algorithm uses different kernel functions for different types to take data as input and transforms it into the required form. A function $K: X \times X \rightarrow R$ is called kernel function (Mercer kernel or simply kernel) if it is symmetric and positive definite:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \Phi^T(x_i) \cdot \Phi(x_j),$$

where $K(x_i, x_j)$ is a function in input space. **Table 1** summarizes the popular admissible kernel functions used in this paper.

Table 1
Admissible kernel functions

Name (Abbreviation)	Definition	Parameter
Linear (Lin.)	$k(x_1, x_2) = x_1 \cdot x_2$	–
Polynomial (Pol.)	$k(x_i, x_j) = (x_i \cdot x_j + 1)^d$	d
Radial basis function (Rad.)	$k(x_i, x_j) = \exp(-\gamma \ x_i - x_j\ ^2)$	γ
Sigmoid (Sig.)	$k(x_i, x_j) = \tanh(\alpha x^T y + c)$	C

ε -Support Vector Regression (ε -SVR) maps the input vectors $x_i \in R^m$ into a high dimensional feature space [18]. Given a training set, (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where $x_i \in R^m$ is the m -dimensional input vector and $y_i \in R$ is the response variable. SVR generates the linear regression function in the form of generic cost estimation model given:

$$f(x, w) = w^T x + b, \quad (4)$$

where w is the weight vector corresponding to x and b is the bias. In contrast to classic regression, Vapnik's linear loss function is defined with ε -insensitivity zone:

$$L(y, f(x)) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } |y - f(x)| \leq \varepsilon; \\ |y - f(x)| - \varepsilon, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The approximation of function f is performed by finding an ε -insensitive tube as flat as possible via minimizing the norm of w . Thus, one tries to minimize the risk R and $\|w\|^2$ simultaneously to construct a linear regression hyperplane in (4) as follows:

$$\text{Minimize } R = \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + c \sum_{i=1}^n |y - f(x)|_{\varepsilon}. \quad (6)$$

Where c is the regularization parameter controlling the trade-off between an approximation error and the weight vector norm w .

Minimizing R is equivalent to minimizing the risk under the following constraints:

$$\text{Minimize } R = \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + c \sum_{i=1}^n (\xi_i + \xi_i^*), \quad (7)$$

$$\text{subject to } \begin{cases} (w^T x_i + b) - y_i \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i, \\ y_i - (w^T x_i + b) \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i^*, \\ \xi_i, \xi_i^* \geq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where ξ_i and ξ_i^* are slack variables for exceeding and lowering the target value by more than ε , respectively.

v – Support Vector Regression (v -SVR) [19] provides a way to automatically minimize ε by introducing the new constant variable $v \in (0, 1)$ [20], which is used as a trade-off against model complexity and slack variables. Given a function $\varphi(x)$ which transforms data from input space to kernel space, the optimization problem is:

$$\min_w \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \left(v\varepsilon + \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l (\xi + \xi^*) \right), \quad (9)$$

$$\text{subject to } \begin{cases} y_i - w^T \varphi(x_i) - b \leq \varepsilon + \xi, \\ w^T \varphi(x_i) + b - y_i \leq \varepsilon + \xi^*, \\ \xi, \xi^*, \varepsilon \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Forming a Lagrangian formulation from $(\varphi = R^d \rightarrow F)$ by introducing positive multipliers α , α^* , η , η^* and b gives:

$$L(w, \xi, \xi^*, \alpha, \alpha^*, \eta, \eta^*, \beta) = \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + Cv\varepsilon + \frac{C}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i^* (y_i - w^T x_i - b - \varepsilon - \xi_i) + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i (w^T x_i + b - y_i - \varepsilon - \xi_i^*) - \sum_{i=1}^l (\eta_i \xi_i + \eta_i^* \xi_i^*) \beta \varepsilon. \quad (10)$$

Following the KKT (Karush-Kuhn-Tucker) conditions that partial derivatives with respect to the variables w , b , x , x^* , and ε are equal to be zero and the products of the Lagrange multipliers and the constraint are equal to zero, we have the following dual optimization problem:

$$\max_{\alpha, \alpha^*} \sum_{i=1}^{l_{sv}} y_i (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{l_{sv}} \sum_{j=1}^{l_{sv}} (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) (\alpha_j - \alpha_j^*) k(x_i, x_j),$$

where

$$k(x_i, x_j) = \varphi(x_i) \varphi(x_j),$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{l_{sv}} (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) = 0, \alpha_i, \alpha_i^* \in \left[0, \frac{C}{l} \right], \sum_{i=1}^{l_{sv}} (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) \leq Cv. \quad (11)$$

Then, the regression estimate takes the form,

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{l_{sv}} (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) k(x_i, x) + b. \quad (12)$$

Renal failure data from Hiwa Hospital in Sulaymaniyah Governorate – Iraq and simulations were conducted for the purpose of comparison between ε -SVR and v -SVR models after and before applying PCA using four different kernel functions to detect the PCA effect on data reduction and to evaluate the performance of ε -SVR and v -SVR models. In this study, all trained models designed are evaluated using measured data based on two different measures, root mean square error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R^2). RMSE is a commonly used measure of the difference between predicted values of model and the actual values from the system that is being modeled. The sample sizes are $n = 50, 100$, and 150 . The simulation results were based on 10000 replications. All computation implemented using the R software, version (Rx64 3.2.5).

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the simulation study show in **Table 2**, that the first two components explain 85 %, 93 %, and 99 % of the variance for all sample sizes.

Table 2
Evaluation of components for all sample size (simulation)

n&Comp. SD, PV& CP	n	Comp. 1	Comp. 2	Comp. 3	Comp. 4	Comp. 5
Standard deviation		2.2460442	1.390897	0.14384427	4.68E-05	2.650258e-
Proportion of variance	50	0.7206735	0.2763706	0.00295588	3.13E-10	1.003410e-
Cumulative proportion		0.7206735	0.9970441	1	1.00E+00	1.000000e+
Standard deviation		1.0079352	0.9613183	0.925273	0.484964	0.071246
Proportion of variance	100	0.7113529	0.142019	0.1223043	0.033599	0.000725
Cumulative proportion		0.7113529	0.8533719	0.9656762	0.999275	1.000000
Standard deviation		2.31928	1.074159	0.523973	0.435453	0.048155
Proportion of variance	150	0.768437	0.164831	0.039221	0.027088	0.000331
Cumulative proportion		0.768437	0.933268	0.972489	0.999578	0.999909

Secondly, this study was conducted on real data about renal failure disease. Renal failure (RF), as it was historically termed, is a term that encompasses all degrees of decreased kidney functions, from damaged, at risk through mild, moderate, and severe chronic kidney failure. RF is a worldwide public health problem. In the United States, there is a rising incidence and prevalence of kidney failure, with poor outcomes and high cost, the variable that used are Gender, Age, Smoking, Drinking, Urea, Creatinine, Calcium, Phosphorus, Alk. Phosphatase, Glucose, and Albumin.

According to the importance of the components, **Table 3** shows that the first two components explain 85 % and 99 % of the variance for all sample sizes for renal failure data.

Table 3
Evaluation of components for all sample size (real data results)

n&Comp. SD, PV& CP	n	Comp. 1	Comp. 2	Comp. 3	Comp. 4	Comp. 5
Standard deviation		2.2460442	1.390897	0.14384427	4.68E-05	–
Proportion of variance	50	0.7206735	0.2763706	0.00295588	3.13E-10	–
Cumulative proportion		0.7206735	0.9970441	1	1.00E+00	–
Standard deviation		1.681815	1.065381	0.484964	0.071246	0.06561
Proportion of variance	100	0.56622	0.292148	0.133599	0.001825	0.006209
Cumulative proportion		0.56622	0.858368	0.991966	0.993791	1
Standard deviation		1.007935	0.961318	0.925273	0.484964	0.0712466
Proportion of variance	150	0.711353	0.142019	0.122304	0.023599	0.0007251
Cumulative proportion		0.711353	0.853372	0.975676	0.999275	1

Real data results displayed in **Table 4** shows that before applying PCA, and with ε -SVR the number of SVR is reduced by 60 %, with the radial kernel which is superior to its counterparts with most sample sizes, then a radial kernel function was followed by the linear and polynomial kernels with respect to performance for this real data. On the other side, with ν -SVR the number of SVR is reduced by 62 % for linear kernel function which is superior to its counterparts for sample sizes 50 and 150. Then after applying PCA with ε -SVR, the percentage of the reduced number of SVR is about 41 % for the linear and radial kernel functions which shows superiority to their counterparts for all most all sample sizes. Then after applying PCA with ν -SVR, the highest percentage of reduction of the number of SVR is for the linear and radial kernel functions.

According to the simulation results in **Table 5**, before applying PCA, the radial kernel for ε -SVR shows superiority for all kernel functions. It reduced the number of SVR by 51 % and the sigmoid kernel for ν -SVR shows superiority for all kernel functions. It reduced the number of SVR by 59 %

Table 4
Number of SVR of ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR (real data results)

Kernel	Using PCA n	ϵ -SVR			ν -SVR		
		50	100	150	50	100	150
Linear	Before	30	60	88	19	59	88
	After	31	70	88	22	43	63
Polynomial	Before	30	60	113	26	55	111
	After	32	68	112	23	43	64
Radial	Before	29	40	88	27	62	87
	After	30	70	89	23	48	68
Sigmoid	Before	37	62	111	23	42	119
	After	39	75	119	21	41	62

Table 5
Number of SVR of ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR (simulation results)

Kernel	Using PCA n	ϵ -SVR			ν -SVR		
		50	100	150	50	100	150
Linear	Before	35	68	80	22	66	63
	After	38	76	71	21	42	63
Polynomial	Before	35	72	86	23	67	65
	After	35	73	75	24	44	70
Radial	Before	38	70	73	24	68	65
	After	39	76	70	24	46	66
Sigmoid	Before	37	77	114	22	79	62
	After	38	79	75	22	41	70

The following figures, **Fig. 1, 2** illustrated the effect of sample size on the RMSE values for real data.

Fig. 1. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR after applying principal component analysis for n (real data results)

Fig. 2. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR after applying principal component analysis for n (real data results)

With ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR and for all sample sizes after applying PCA, and for real data as shown in **Fig. 1, 2**, it is clear that the root mean square error with linear and radial kernel functions decreased with increasing sample size. But the greatest values for RMSE were for $n = 100$

with sigmoid kernel function. But, for simulation results with sample size $n = 50$ have good results for the linear, and the radial kernel functions as shown in **Fig. 3, 4**.

The following figures, **Fig. 5–7**, show the effects of PCA with small, moderate, and large sample size with ϵ -SVR before and after applying PCA for real data. And, it can be concluded that for all sample sizes the performance of ϵ -SVR improved after applying PCA. Also, it is clear that the root mean square error with linear and radial kernel functions gave the best results than other kernel functions. In addition, the sigmoid kernel gave the worst result amongst the other kernel functions.

Fig. 3. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR after applying principal component analysis for n (simulation results)

Fig. 4. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR after applying principal component analysis for n (simulation results)

Fig. 5. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 50$ (real data results)

Fig. 6. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 100$ (real data results)

Fig. 7. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 150$ (real data results)

For simulation results **Fig. 8–10**, and for all sample sizes $n = 50, 100$, and 150 , it can be concluded that the performance of ϵ -SVR improved after applying PCA for linear, radial and sigmoid kernels.

Fig. 8. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying pincipal component analysis for $n = 50$ (simulation results)

Fig. 9. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying pincipal component analysis for $n = 100$ (simulation results)

Fig. 10. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR before & after applying pincipal component analysis for $n = 150$ (simulation results)

With ν -SVR, and for all sample sizes $n = 50, 100$, and 150 , from figures, **Fig. 11–13**, it can be concluded that the performance of ν -SVR improved after applying PCA except for polynomial kernel for $n = 50$ and for sigmoid kernel for $n = 150$.

Fig. 11. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR before & after applying pincipal component analysis for $n = 50$ (real data results)

Fig. 12. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR before & after applying pincipal component analysis for $n = 100$ (real data results)

Fig. 13. Root mean squared error of v -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 150$ (real data results)

For simulation results with v -SVR, **Fig. 14** shows that for linear and radial kernels the performance of v -SVR improved after applying PCA, and for $n = 50$ and $n = 150$, sigmoid kernel gave the worst results amongst the other kernel functions and did not improved after PCA application **Fig. 14–16**.

For the following figures **Fig. 17–20**, it is clear that for all types of kernel functions and for all sample sizes ϵ -SVR is better than v -SVR after applying PCA, except for $n = 50$ for radial and sigmoid kernel functions and for $n = 150$ for sigmoid kernel.

Fig. 14. Root mean squared error of v -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 50$ (simulation results)

Fig. 15. Root mean squared error of v -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 100$ (simulation results)

Fig. 16. Root mean squared error of v -SVR before & after applying principal component analysis for $n = 150$ (simulation results)

Fig. 17. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for linear kernel (after applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 18. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for radial kernel (after applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 19. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for polynomial kernel (after applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 20. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for sigmoid kernel (after applying principal component analysis)

And for almost types of kernel functions and for all sample sizes ϵ -SVR results are better than ν -SVR results before applying PCA as shown in the figures from **Fig. 21–24**.

The two figures **Fig. 25, 26** illustrate the effects of kernel functions on RMSE with ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR, for all sample sizes, after applying PCA.

Fig. 21. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for linear kernel (before applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 22. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for radial kernel (before applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 23. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for polynomial kernel (before applying principal component analysis)

Fig. 24. Root mean squared error of support vector regression for sigmoid kernel (before applying principal component analysis)

According to the results for ϵ -SVR, **Fig. 25**, the linear kernel function gave the best value for the RMSE then the radial kernel function. But the sigmoid kernel function gave the worst value. It is worth noting that with the increase in the sample size, the results for linear and radial kernel functions become close to each other.

Also, the results for ν -SVR are very similar to the results for ϵ -SVR except for sample size $n = 100$ the polynomial kernel function gave the worst RMSE value, and for sample size $n = 150$ the sigmoid kernel function also gave the worst RMSE value, **Fig. 26**.

These results are similar to results before applying PCA as shown in **Fig. 27, 28**.

Fig. 25. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR for all kernels after applying principal component analysis (real data results)

Fig. 26. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR for all kernels after applying principal component analysis (real data results)

In general, the principal component analysis method has some limitations, such that it may reduce some important variables and their individual effect may not be considered. Also, it may eliminate variables that can have an effect in the application and in the practice.

All results are shown in the **Tables 6, 7**.

Fig. 27. Root mean squared error of ϵ -SVR for all kernels before applying principal component analysis (simulation results)

Fig. 28. Root mean squared error of ν -SVR for all kernels before applying principal component analysis (simulation results)

Table 6

Real data results for ϵ -SVR and ν -SVR for all sample size and for all kernel functions

Kernel	n	Using PCA	ϵ -SVR		ν -SVR		
			RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	
Linear	50	Before	12.847	0.98615	3.999997	0.9999997	
		After	3.1006	0.79553	1.716787	0.799017	
Polynomial		Before	60.8	0.61521	10.80026	0.5759938	
		After	81.332	0.58601	30.77085	0.5851366	
Radial		Before	11.145	0.91842	10.58939	0.9272886	
		After	3.1075	0.774	5.677752	0.7789302	
Sigmoid		Before	147.9	0.22172	35.56564	0.3235271	
		After	123.29	0.29033	27.24618	0.3354484	
Linear		100	Before	0.93834	4.076746	0.99999	13.361
			After	0.70107	3.048943	0.72162	8.1918
Polynomial	Before		0.00788	13.54168	0.80754	51.528	
	After		0.80555	9.2942	0.70836	29.815	
Radial	Before		0.83469	11.23287	0.85455	33.35	
	After		0.74132	2.67359	0.7727	19.071	
Sigmoid	Before		0.00566	137.1549	0.80892	63.24	
	After		2.43E-05	102.8212	0.00036	50.192	
Linear	150		Before	0.88255	12.85747	0.989993	11.585
			After	0.88681	3.155632	0.89850873	2.2034
Polynomial		Before	0.99995	54.41528	0.965231	77.599	
		After	0.88069	55.52714	0.89263741	20.998	
Radial		Before	0.69855	12.45879	0.854785	14.25	
		After	0.85871	2.80651	0.74961282	2.9778	
Sigmoid		Before	0.02587	102.3265	0.074866	987.64	
		After	0.02122	105.6884	0.0273304	346.19	

Table 7Simulation results for ε -SVR and ν -SVR for all sample size and for all kernel functions

Kernel	n	Using PCA	ε -SVR		ν -SVR		
			RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	
Linear	50	Before	0.0923984	0.1485413	0.0753	0.89941	
		After	0.01705531	0.9704997	0.0281	0.93996	
Polynomial		Before	0.09449996	0.0933367	0.0895	0.04044	
		After	0.1129674	0.0109321	0.1018	0.1128	
Radial		Before	0.07145724	0.1615464	0.1672	0.09989	
		After	0.07087877	0.1213056	0.0724	0.54475	
Sigmoid		Before	0.951324	0.0714112	0.1204	0.11041	
		After	0.8962571	0.1213056	0.83	0.04193	
Linear		100	Before	3.0601	0.655535	14.04	0.71355
			After	0.669	0.852525	7.8355	0.9543
Polynomial	Before		4.6058	0.42215	46.756	0.47307	
	After		4.9318	0.02155	9.1136	0.12259	
Radial	Before		3.4027	0.50777	14.669	0.54595	
	After		0.4429	0.54111	10.065	0.71345	
Sigmoid	Before		7.2199	0.07103	70.519	0.03979	
	After		10.148	0.02523	29.112	0.08775	
Linear	150		Before	5.1164	0.65972	10.489	0.605545
			After	1.7035	0.78457	2.3699	0.9101
Polynomial		Before	10.964	0.45217	12.536	0.47863	
		After	2.541	0.54872	6.9917	0.1665	
Radial		Before	5.7075	0.60955	10.975	0.59872	
		After	1.841	0.7746	2.6763	0.9121	
Sigmoid		Before	45.763	0.13455	38.458	0.20802	
		After	24.496	0.1231	62.005	0.0037	

4. Conclusions

It is important not to lose more information than is necessary, when reducing the data dimensions. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a well-established mathematical technique for reducing the dimensionality of data, while keeping as much variation as possible as noted in application. It is also known that using of SVR with various kernel functions improves the estimated models. The behavior for two different models ε -SVR and ν -SVR are compared through real data and simulation study for four different kernel functions: linear, radial, polynomial, and sigmoid kernel functions, for different sample sizes. Generally, the real data results shows that before applying PCA, and with ε -SVR and ν -SVR the number of SVR is reduced in average from 30 % to 48 % and from 35 % to 54 % respectively. But, after applying PCA, and with ε -SVR and ν -SVR the number of SVR is reduced in average from 23 % to 38 % and from 54 % to 59 % respectively. Thus, it becomes apparent that, the reduced number of SVR after and before PCA application using ν -SVR is more than that of ε -SVR. On the other hand, the simulation results shows that before applying PCA, and with ε -SVR and ν -SVR the reduced number of SVR ranges from 24 % to 38 % and from 43 % to 50 % respectively. But, after applying PCA, and with ε -SVR and ν -SVR the reduced number of SVR ranges from 31 % to 37 % and from 53 % to 58 % respectively. Also clearly shown, the reduced number of SVR after and before PCA application with ν -SVR is more than that of ε -SVR.

It is also clear that, with ε -SVR and ν -SVR, the RMSE values for almost kernel functions decreased with increasing sample size. This means that both application and simulation results are consistent with the theory. And, for all kernel functions and for all sample sizes ε -SVR results in

terms of RMSE are better than v -SVR results before and after applying PCA. Therefore, the performance of ε -SVR improved after applying PCA for both real data and simulation. In addition, for all sample sizes, sample size $n = 50$ gave good results for linear and radial kernel functions.

The disadvantages of this study, which must be considered, are the small number of variables and the small size of the samples. Both may have an effect in the shown result. Therefore, it is recommended in the future to study the defects resulting from sampling and non-sampling errors. It can also be recommended to use regular multivariate techniques that do not reduce the variables such as factor analysis and cluster analysis methods. In addition, and in the context of reduction, it is proposed to study if the reduced one is important to the study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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